

UZBEK WOMEN IN INTERNATIONAL ARENAS

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Annotation: This article discusses the attention paid to women's sports today and the opportunities, conditions and their results, the results of our athletes in the international arena.

Keywords: Special Olympics, Women's Committee, Special Olympics, Paralympic Games, sports, world arenas

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, "Respect for women, respect for women is a noble value of our people. We, all of us, no matter what profession, no matter what position we work in, are forever indebted to you, kind women, for all the virtues in our hearts and souls.

In particular, you, the saints, your role and service in raising a healthy, harmoniously developed generation cannot be compared with anything¹.

Today, along with the development of women's sports in our country, special attention is paid to the development of sports among women with disabilities. In particular, the annual Special Olympics, the Women's Committee's special spartakiads for girls with mental disabilities, paralympic spartakiads are an example of this².

Raising a healthy generation begins in early childhood. The means of physical culture, especially sports, play an important role in this. Indeed, the future of a country with healthy children is bright, and a lot of positive work is being done in this regard. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of the Fund for the Development of Children's Sports in Uzbekistan"³ and a special resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers were adopted on this basis⁴.

It is known that in all developed countries of the world, attention and love for women are paramount. The level of development of a society is also determined by the attitude towards women.

Today, the most common disease among women is anemia, which occurs as a result of congenital or environmental disorders. There are also many women who are overweight (obesity), osteochondrosis (salt accumulation), osteoarthritis and arthritis (inflammation of the joints). All this indicates that they are inactive, do not pay attention to exercise. Most importantly, all of this affects their reproductive health. In both cases, the state of health as a result of exercise, especially rhythmic gymnastics, rather than drugs, is based on scientific and practical experience. For this reason, the use of physical education and treatment centers in the treatment of various diseases in the central cities is increasing day by day.

In 2004, at the initiative of the Republican Women's Committee and the National

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Milliy taraqqiyot yo'limizni qat'iyat bilan davom ettirib, yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz. – T.: O'zbekiston, 2018. B. 342.

² Report of the Women's Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2004, 2005, 2006.

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-3154. 24.10.2002.

⁴ Collection of decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. №374, October 31, 2002.

Olympic Committee, the Commission on Women and Sports was established. Its main goal is to promote and develop women's sports. In order to promote and promote women's sports, the Commission held a competition "Queen of Sports", which promotes youth, beauty and a healthy lifestyle. Athlete girls showed that they can be not only strong and strong-willed athletes, but also gentle and agile housewives.

In recent years, the state pays great attention to the development of women's sports. Sports that only women can do include rhythmic gymnastics and synchronized swimming. In 2004-2005, for the first time in the history of rhythmic gymnastics, the Sharq Guzali World Cup was held at a high level. The strongest athletes of the world, Olympic and world champions Alina Kabaeva, Olga Kapranova, Vera Sesina took part in it. Along with them, Uzbek gymnasts O.Ashaeva and Z.Mukhitdinova took honorable places. Since 1998, the Mermaid International Synchronized Swimming Competition has been held at a high level.

Special attention is paid to the type of rhythmic gymnastics in the promotion of sports among women. For example, U.Trofimova successfully participated in the World Championship in Montpellier, France, and for the first time won a ticket to the 2012 Olympics in this field⁵.

Oksana Chusovitina has a special place in women's sports in Uzbekistan. She achieved great success and participated in 7 Olympic Games (1992, 1996, 2000, 2004, 2008, 2012, 2016). Oksana Chusovitina's career in rhythmic gymnastics lasted more than 28 years and was included in the Guinness Book of Records.

Luiza Ganieva is a multiple regional and Uzbek champion in rhythmic gymnastics (2010). Winner of the Asian Championship 2010 bronze medal. Member of the national team.

Having learned the secrets of this sport from an experienced coach Vera Kataeva since 2002, Louise has been among the winners and prize-winners of several international tournaments. In 2009 he won gold medals at international tournaments in Bukhara and Germany. In 2008, he won a bronze medal at an international tournament in Russia.

The active participation of our women in all sports testifies to the fact that our women are equal members of our society.

In 2006, in order to develop women's sports, by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 221 additional places for women were created at the UZSDI, which were distributed (91 state grants, 130 contracts) by region. The main reason for this is the need for women with higher education for all regions of the country. In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of physical culture and sports among women, especially in the training of highly qualified specialists from local women R.A. Koziyeva (history of physical education), O. Sobirova (swimming, deceased), K.T. The contribution of such scientists as Rakhimjanova (Shokirjonova - athletics), R.A. Kasimova (handball), G.B. Abdurasulova (fencing) is great. It is very important in the future to increase the number of such talented scientists⁶.

In short, the attention paid to women's sports today and the opportunities and conditions created are bearing fruit. One by one, our athletes are achieving high results in the international arena.

⁵ Noveyshaya istoriya Uzbekistana. Uchebnik pod red. d.i.n., prof. M.A.Raximova. - T.: Adabiyot uchqunlari. 2018. Str. 304.

⁶ Kaziyeva R.I Razvitiye jenskogo fizkulturnogo dvijeniya v Uzbekistane. -T.: Uzbekistan, 1979. -S.142.

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